

HERITAGE QUEST: A GAMIFIED HISTORICAL LEARNING EXPERIENCE**Elian, Eldrian Rey P.¹, Gaddi, Dicol D.², Gaddy, Nhio James B.³, Gallentes, Ralph Justine I.⁴, and Fernandez, Ronald B.⁵**^{1,2,3,4,5} College of Computing Studies, Universidad De Manila, Manila, Metro Manila, Philippines**ABSTRACT**

HERITAGE QUEST: A Gamified Historical Learning Experience is a working educational app, designed to facilitate the learning of Philippine history through community interaction, and gamification. The app is developed using Unity and C#, and the game applies gaming and artificial intelligence. By utilizing a 3D virtual map, players can move around Metro Manila, interact with NPCs driven by AI, visit heritage sites and take quizzes that assess their learning. The app also will track usage and motivation with a leaderboard and achievements. Using a development-oriented design, and a guided agile process, the project took development iterative steps to support the development of the app. The app is designed for phone and tablet use to reach fluent operation and performance. The app, in its current iteration, employs assessments and has a limited number of heritage sites, with limited support for accessibility, such as narration of text and changing the text font size. In its current version, HERITAGE QUEST express an vision of gamified education making historical education and learning not only fun and meaningful but culturally responsive. Future development will have more content, more accessible methodology, and an impact assessment of educational use.

Keywords:

Gamified learning, NPC, Artificial intelligence, 3D virtual map, C#, Unity

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a fast-paced computer science field that makes machines learn like human beings, conduct complicated problem-solving tasks, and optimize decision-making. It covers many subdisciplines such as machine learning, deep learning, natural language processing, and computer vision that help systems to learn from examples, identify patterns, and make data-driven decisions without direct coding. With the ongoing development of Artificial Intelligence (AI), its application in various fields, such as education and gaming, has become more prominent, offering interactive and engaging means to enrich learning experiences.

The system to be proposed is an interactive adventure learning game that integrates historical discovery with interactive learning. Such a game will have a virtual map where the players will be able to traverse different sites of historical importance, such as famous historical tourist spots in Metro Manila. Along the way, each place that the players visit will have associated historical information and learning activities that reveal the historical importance of each site. One of the essential elements of the game is asking players to provide answers to a series of questions about the historical information they acquired before moving to the next site. Interactive narration will build a more immersive and interactive learning environment. The game will also include AI-powered NPCs that provide hints and explanations, making learning easier and more interactive. To encourage participation, at the end of the game, we will have a leaderboard system and achievements for players who complete all challenges and quizzes correctly. Players who successfully visit all historical sites and answer all questions will unlock a final historical narrative or special achievement, marking their completion as a 'Master Historian' or equivalent title. By combining AI-driven storytelling and interactive quizzes, HERITAGE QUEST offers an exciting way to experience history and challenge players to become experts in historical learning.

The main goal of this project is to create an interactive educational game that extends historical knowledge and interest through exploration and quizzes. The game wants to create interest and appreciation of local history in students and players by making available historical information in a gamification format. Also, it wishes to enhance critical thinking, problem-solving, and memory skills by means of interactive learning activities. The project further seeks to enhance digital literacy and learning gamification through the incorporation of technology into learning approaches.

Pointed out that the integration of local history and geography using interactive digital media can have a strong positive impact on students' interest in civic participation and historical consciousness. Using emerging technologies and interactive learning practices, this project hopes to create an innovative learning tool that increases historical learning through interactive gameplay [1].

II. OBJECTIVES

This study aims to develop an AI-powered gamified historical learning experience that enhances student engagement, improves historical knowledge retention and fosters a greater appreciation for cultural heritage through interactive storytelling and discovery. This study specific objectives will focus on the following:

- To implement gamification features such as quizzes, challenges, achievements, and leaderboards.
- To design and develop an interactive virtual environment where users can explore historically significant sites in Metro Manila.
- To integrate AI NPCs that provide real-time guidance, hints, and explanations to enhance learning and engagement.
- To develop an intuitive and user-friendly interface suitable for students, educators, and casual learners.

III. METHODOLOGY

The research design, development model, data collection methods, system architecture, implementation tools, and evaluation processes adopted in the design and development of “Heritage Quest: A Gamified Historical Learning Experience”. The methodology is rigorous and has been completely organized such that the project was designed, intervened, and evaluated along the way, providing evidence of success by achieving historical learning through gamification and artificial intelligence.

2.1 Research Design

The research employed a developmental research design using mixed methods. The developmental research design provided a framework for the design, development, and testing while the mixed-methods model allowed the evaluation of the system through qualitative and quantitative methods for usability, user engagement, and learning outcomes.

- Development Approach – The system was designed to be a AI-powered gamified application, with the following features AI driven NPCs, quizzes and an virtual interactive map of historical sites in Metro Manila.
- Experimental Approach – The application will be deployed in controlled tests, and the levels of user engagement, user retention and user performance, using the application and other heritage apps, will be compared to rolled our people’s history learning in schools.

2.2 System Development Model

Figure 1: Agile Development Model

The Agile Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) allowed the same of development in rapid cycles while providing flexibility and continuous engagement of feedback from the users.

Phases of Development:

- **Planning** - In this phase, project stewardship was undertaken by defining the project scope and objectives, ensuring requirements were met and researched Metro Manila's historical sites.
- **Design** - In this phase, the system architecture, UI design and system prototype was conceptualized, alongside a 3D virtual map to enhance user experience.
- **Development** - This phase was devoted to developing the main functional aspects of the system, such as NPCs with AI capability for historical storytelling, quizzes and data storage for leaderboards, through Unity using the C# language.
- **Testing** - At this stage system testing was undertaken to validate the stability and document accuracy of the system before it was released.
- **Deployment** - The system was released for pilot testing with the target user group and bugs/issues remained monitored for feedback by developers.
- **Evaluation and Refinement** - Using user feedback (and their usage data recorded), a refinement of the system took place for improvement including performance and experience improvements.

2.3 Data Gathering Techniques

- **Primary Data** – Surveys, interviews, and user testing sessions over the project's lifetime with students, teachers and tourism specialists were recorded to understand engagement, usability and learning impact.
- **Secondary Data** – A review of literature and prior studies on gamification, the use of AI in education and historical learning was conducted. Historical sources from verified sources were reached to obtain the pieces of integrated system content for accuracy.

2.4 Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to ethical guidelines pertaining to informed consent, privacy and sensitivity to culture. Participants were informed that participation in surveys and tests was voluntary - clear information was provided on the intent and procedures of the study. Participants were informed that their participation was voluntary, screened out of the study at any time, and their responses would be confidentially kept and used for research purposes only. For the historical content, verification of facts was performed, and content was evaluated for cultural sensitivity. Accessibility concerns were considered in future versions. The amount of data gathered was minimal, safeguarded, and kept confidential with technological security. Intellectual property rights were respected by using content in the public domain or content licensed for use.

IV. MODELING AND ANALYSIS

Table 1. Tools and Materials Used in Heritage Quest: A Gamified Historical Learning Experience

COMPONENTS	TECHNOLOGY	USED
Programming Language	C#	Used to develop core game logic, NPC interactions, quiz mechanics, and player tracking.
Game Development Engine	Unity	Used for creating interactive 3D environments and handling user input and animations.
Database Management System	PlayerPrefs (JSON file)	Stores player data, quiz results, and progress for retrieval between sessions.
Framework	.NET Framework	Supports backend components, database integration, and communication between game engine and interface.
Hardware	Windows PC	The system is optimized for use on Windows PCs, utilizing their processing power for real-time interactions.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the development and evaluation of HERITAGE QUEST: A Gamified Historical Learning Experience. The system was based on the combined of gamification, artificial intelligence and historical places in a learning environment. The concept was to provide a space for users to explore a 3D virtual map of Metro Manila, engage with NPCs powered by AI, answer site-based quizzes, and understand their progress on a leaderboard with a set of achievements. The development for HERITAGE QUEST was conducted using Agile methodology: requirements analysis, design, development, testing, and user evaluation. This chapter offers an account of the projects system implementation outcomes: performance testing and survey results; user evaluation based on the ISO 9126-1 standards for software quality; and discusses the implications of our findings that were obtained from participants and inquires into the system strengths, weaknesses, and avenues for improvement, to assess an application useful for historical learning and cultural engagement.

4.1 SYSTEM EVALUATION

- **Functional Suitability:** All players expressed the app's quizzes, NPC guidance and advancement system as valuable in learning about the history of Metro Manila as it relates to their in-game experience. The app received an average score of 4.26 / 5.
- **Performance Efficiency:** The app had very short load time and navigation was easily initiated. A consistent respond rate was observed even after long periods of playing, as well as good functionality across all midrange devices. The Overall score in this area was 4.20 / 5.
- **Usability:** User's perceived the user interface as easy to use, visually appealing, and nice to read the clarity surrounding instructions and quiz question content. Users also liked the ease of navigating the VR map. Overall score given for this dimension was 4.16 / 5.
- **Maintainability:** Other users expressed that this system could also be easily modified and updated. Based on their perspective, historical elements, quizzes, and other features, could be added to the app, and potentially the main app structure would require only minor shedding of old content and adding new structure. Maintainability score was 4.16 / 5.
- **Reliability:** The application was reliable throughout testing. It did not crash, freeze, and progress was save every time. The application reopened successfully during testing. This was the highest score 4.32/5.
- **Compatibility:** Users indicated that the app was compatible for use on a variety of devices and a variety of brands. It installs, coexists with other apps use and has further potential to be taken to other platforms. Compatibility rated a 4.32/5.
- **Portability:** Moving, installing, reinstalling, and switching devices was very easy. Users experienced retained progress after reinstalling the app, and some users expected the program to expand to other platforms in future enhancements. The average score was 4.26/5.

Figure1: Shows the overall result rates in different criteria

Criteria	Description	Average Rating (5 point scale)
Functional Suitability	Does the game meet your learning and exploration needs effectively?	4.26
Performance Efficiency	How well does the system perform during gameplay	4.2
Usability	Is the system easy and comfortable to use	4.16
Security	Does the system protect your data and usage	4.22
Maintainability	Can the system be updated and maintained easily	4.16
Reliability	Is the system stable and available when you need it	4.32
Compatibility	Does the system work with various devices or systems	4.32
Portability	Can the system be reused or installed in different environments easily	4.26

VI. CONCLUSION

This study outline the development process, evaluation, and incorporation of the feedback into HERITAGE QUEST: A Gamified Historical Learning Experience, and AI-powered interactive game that puts Metro Manila heritage sites on a virtual 3D map, provides narratives of each site with quiz associated with each narrative, and utilizes AI-powered NPCs with an assignment based interaction to engage the learners. HERITAGE QUEST used Unity and C# to design the system that was evaluated using pilot studies, surveys, and the user's experience sessions with university students and local tourism stakeholders. The evaluation provided an overall positive and meeting the ISO quality attributes (functionality, efficiency, usability, security, reliability, compatibility, and portability), which these attributes indicated that the system performed well and users satisfied. The game has performed well with high ratings by the user community, and will require further development of content, increased accessibility features, and larger scale testing.

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VIII. REFERENCES

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